

EASY SOLUTION OF SOME GEOMETRIC PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

The main point is the enrichment of the spatial imagination of the readers with the idea of creating new ideas and ideas.

РЕЗЮМЕ

Главное-обогащать пространственное воображение читателей идей создание новых идей и идей.

Key words: *bisector, median, trapeziod, similarity, height, vertical angles, arc, parallel straight lines.*

One of the most important requirements for improving the quality of education is to arouse interest and activity among students. This can be achieved by correctly and skillfully presenting the new material. As a result of the presentation of given which the questions asked by the teacher can be sloved should be clear to the students. Their interest in the subject will increase only when the presentation of a new topic is carried out with the active participation of all students. While thinking about the next lesson, the teacher should have clearly in mind the purpose of this lesson, so that this lesson creates new concepts and ideas in the students and makes them gain some new knowledge. When planning lessons, it is necessary to pay special attention to each of its elements, such as asking questions, explaining a new topic, repeating. We present

examples of problems that will help students expand their geometric imagination and enrich their thinking.

Issue 1

Prove that the medians of triangles are divided in the ratio 2:1 at the point of intersection.

The purpose of proving these problems is that there are many problems that can be solved using the proof of this problem.

Proof:

According to the median property- $CK=KB$, $AN=NB$.

It is enough for us to prove- $\frac{CO}{ON} = 2$.

We make a cross section CM parallel to AB , where an additional figure CKM triangle is formed. Hence $\triangle AKB = \triangle CKM$

$\angle KAB = \angle KMC$; $\angle ABK = \angle MCK$ (according to the property of internal alternating angles)

$\angle AKB = \angle CKM$ –vertical angles. $\triangle AKB \sim \triangle CKM$ from $CK:KB=CM:AB=1$, hence

It is derived - $CM=AB$.

There will also be $\triangle AON \sim \triangle COM$. $CO:ON=CM:AN=2$, because $2AN=AB=CM$.We get the result $CO=2ON$. **It has been proven.**

Issue 2

Find $AB = ?$. Here $BC=4$, $AD=11$ and AH (height) is bisector for altitude $\angle BAD$.

(look at the picture2)

Solution: We pass BF parallel to CD as an auxiliary line. The section BF from the line $CD \parallel BF$ is perpendicular to the section AH .

$BCDF$ is parallelogram. $BC=FD=4$; $AD - FD = AF = 7$; $\triangle BAF$ is equilateral triangle, because

2-picture

AG (height) is bisector $\angle BAD$. Thus, it follows that

$AF=AB=7$. **result: $AB=7$**

Issue 3

Find $S(AED)$ according to the figure. $AB=4$; $EC=6$; $AE \parallel DC$; $AB \perp BC$;

Solution: $\triangle AEC$ is auxiliary figure; $AECD$ -trapeziod. Hence

$S(ECK)=S(ADK)$;

(surfaces of adjacent triangles are equal)

$S(AEC)=S(AED)$, because, $S(AEC)=S(AEK)+S(ECK)$; $S(AED)=S(AEK)+S(AKD)$;
i.e. $S(ECK)=S(ADK)$

$$S(AEC)=S(AED)=\frac{1}{2}AB \cdot EC =12$$

result: $S(AED)=12$.

Issue 4

The largest of the parallel sides of the trapezoid is a , the smallest is b , the non-parallel sides are c and d .

Find the area of the trapezoid.

Solution: The auxiliary figure is a triangle.

We calculate $S_{\Delta} = \sqrt{p(p-c)(p-b)(p-a+b)}$; $p = \frac{1}{2}(a-b+c+d)$;

We find the height $S_{\Delta} = \frac{1}{2}(a-b)h$.

$$h = \frac{1}{2(a-b)} \sqrt{(c+d+a-b)(c+d+b-a)(a-b-c+d)(c+a-b-d)}$$

This height will also be the height of the trapezoid.

Result

$$S_T = \frac{a+b}{2} h =$$

$$\frac{a+b}{4(a-b)} \sqrt{(c+d+a-b)(c+d+b-a)(a-b-c+d)(c+a-b-d)}$$

Issue 5.

A circle whose radius is equal to R is crossed by mutually perpendicular lines AB and CD . Prove that $AD^2 + CB^2 = 4R^2$.

Proof: $\angle CBA = \angle ADC = \angle AKC$ because an

arc is drawn .

According to the right triangle property; $\angle CBA = \angle KCD$. It follows that CK and AD are equal. (CK is auxiliary figure)

$\triangle BCK$ It follows for $\triangle BCK$ that $CB^2 + CK^2 = KB^2 = 4R^2$. Thus, it follows $CB^2 + AD^2 = 4R^2$ by $CK=AD$.

It has been proved.

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